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Environmental Determinants and their Impact on Children's Development and Future Achievements in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The article examines some environmental determinants and their impact on children's development and future achievements in life. In achieving the objectives, the paper begins by presenting the relationship between environment and child development, environmental influences and their impact on child development. Environmental determinants such as physical, social, economic, as well as emotional and educational, have been highlighted as they influence children's development and future achievements. The paper further discusses the influence and obstacles of the environment on children's achievement in life. The paper concludes that, different environmental factors influence children's attitudes. Also, suggestions for a change of attitudes have been made.

Keywords: Environment, determinants, children, development, achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Environment refers to all the circumstances, people, things and events around, that influence people's life. It also refers to the particular surroundings in which people live or exist, especially a region that has particular land sea, or weather conditions. According to Freedman (1981), environment includes broad spectrum of force that affect our daily lives. To Foster et al (1994), environment is anything that surrounds one including family, friends, teachers, neighbourhood and the society. They further maintain that since the time one is born, their environment helps to shape their emotions, attitudes and interests. In addition, Boulton (1996) believes that pollution, which is part of the environment, in all its forms, is harmful and that environmental factors such as contamination and dietary deficiency may affect child development and later achievement in life.

Furthermore, Hurlock (1996) maintains that environment influences the personality pattern in mainly three ways firstly, it encourages the maturation of hereditary potentials, second, it provides personality pattern models and third, it either provides or denies needed learning opportunities.

Thus, the article discusses how environmental determinants and their impact relate to child development and achievement in life.

Relation between Environment and the Child

There are two major environmental determinants which are physical environment and social environment. The physical environment refers to urban design, access to green spaces and housing quality. The social environment refers to parenting practices, social cohesion and peer influences. Others are economic environment (which deals with socio-economic status) poverty and access to resources. Then, the climate change which has its effect on health and developmental opportunities on the child. Also, there are the impacts of all the above on the child achievement in life. So, the article discusses the determinants in the following order.

Family as an Environmental Determinant

Glosson & Smock (1997) state that family is often defined as a group of individuals who share common values, goals and resources. Each family member is responsible for certain decision and they

all share emotional bonds. No two families are the same, yet most families perform certain functions that set them apart from other groups e.g. providing, nurturing and guiding. Family helps to shape one's personality. The individual learns how to think and act mainly from his/her parents. The family teaches one values and what is important in life. It provides food, clothing and shelter. More importantly, it is the family that gives love and emotional support. The love that individual receives as a child helps him or her to form satisfying relationships as an adult.

In addition, communication skills learnt in the family help family members to take active part in the larger society. It is therefore obvious that the individuals do not develop in isolation. It is the nuclear family and extended family that provide the most immediate context within which a child acquires the skills to cope with the environment. Family influences are obviously important during the early stages of human development, but we must recognize that they persist and nourish or defeat our progress throughout life. For instance, a warm relationship with a father figure is important during the early school years and psychosexual difficulties may occur when children identify predominantly with the opposite sex parent. Aggression in children may be expressed by a number of different behaviours. There is by now a substantial amount of evidence that parents of aggressive children tend to use power assertive techniques. It has been hypothesized that physical punishment frustrates children and reinforces their aggressive impulses.

In addition, parents who use physical punishment offer a model of aggressive behaviour. Finally, some parents who punish their children's aggressive behaviour towards themselves also encourage such behaviour towards others. By contrast, the authoritative discipline described earlier reduces aggression by teaching a child concern for others and by pointing out the consequences of aggressive behaviour. (Birren, et al., 1981).

Friends as Environmental Determinants

The origin of friendship in childhood occurs as playmates take on the role of confidants who can communicate with each other, seek advice, and tolerate criticism. During childhood friends are most frequently chosen from children of similar age, sex and level of maturity. Perhaps one's best friends form groups. Friends become very important as one enters his or her teens. Some friends become acquaintances; that is relationship with people one does not know very well e.g. a school mate, co-worker or neighbor. Friendship can enrich a person's life. Although friends are important for individuals to experience feeling of love and security, it is the social group that tends to be next in importance to the parents in providing models for social interaction and the adoption of values. Such values may be positive if they are exerted by constructive religious and other responsible social groups, or they be largely negative when espoused by gangs and associations formed to protect the interest and social isolation of narrow minded and self-interested group (Atechley, 1980).

Friends influence social development in three areas and they relate to establishment of achievement motivation, the motivation to conform and the development of self-concept. For instance, one basic need of adolescents is to establish a separate identity from parents and this can be done primarily by independent patterns of achievement. Through identification with a peer group adolescents can with greater security, learn to think independently and to try other values not necessarily acceptable to their families, while receiving some reinforcement from the group (Douvan and Adelson, 1966 in Birren 1981). Adult social groups on the other hand, tend to be related and primarily around work related and leisure interest activities. Yet, they continue to have an important role in permitting continued growth of feelings of personal identity and recognition of worth. They can also serve as a guilt-reducing mechanism when an individual participates in groups that endorse attitudes and value that are seen as being rationally unacceptable but that, have much emotional appeal.

Teachers and School Administration as Environmental Determinants

Although the primary purpose of the school system may be described as the societal mechanism to teach children skills needed to function in a complex society, it also serves as an important mechanism for the transmission of cultural values and as a socializing agent. Other matters of concern are the way in which discipline is used, the emphasis on academic versus social achievement, and the extent to which the school seeks to transmit and enforce the value system of the majority culture.

Besides the peer influence (friends), the school exposes children directly to the influence of teachers and administers directly to the policy-making roles of school boards. Teachers and administrators set up expectations and norms for discipline, academic performance, and social interaction. These expectations may be influenced by a number of variables that influence the decision maker's

stereotypes. For example, expectations may be set by a teacher's experience with an older sibling or by a teacher identification of a student as being an under achiever on the basis of comparing performance on intelligence tests with classroom behaviour (Plate and Eubank, 1994).

Neighborhood, Community and Society as Environmental Determinants

Beyond one's family, school and work place, the individual is a part of his/her neighborhood, the community and society. It is paramount that the relationship in these larger groups would also help determine the person's future. Individuals, families, and communities have innate peace as part of the gift from God. It is socialization, the process by which society rears its citizens and shapes the attitudes and behaviours of its members, that determines how people handle their problems in the community in the daily work of maintaining itself (Bouldin, 1998). Family members can have good relationships with people outside the family. Maintaining some attitude of friendliness and openness towards others does this. Families become involved in some projects in their neighborhood or community. Examples are community banks, hospitals, schools and even the joint construction of roads and boreholes for portable water.

Impact of Teachers' Personalities

According to Newman & Neman (1988) there are many evidences gathered concerning the effect of teachers' personalities on the social development of children. Well-adjusted teachers express positive and accepting attitudes and thereby motivate children to conform to the school's expectations. Teachers with a positive self-concept in turn are reasonable in their expectations and will facilitate opportunities for successful experiences, thus developing favourable self-concepts in their students. On the other hand, teachers with problems set up conditions of confrontation and arbitrary interactions. Thus, providing a model that child imitates to disadvantage. Such behaviour models teach children to develop feelings of inadequacy and hostility towards authority figures in general.

Impact of the Environmental Factors

The relationship with one's family, friends help fulfill one's needs for affection, love and a sense of belonging. The individual also looks to the family, friends, teachers, coaches and counselors or administrators for acceptance, a hug, a pat on the back and a word of praise to help feel appreciated and loved. Spending time together with friends and family members helps feel that one is part of a group, which cares about the persons. Relationships are important because they allow people to share ideas, feelings and experiences with other persons. The principal raw materials of personality physique, intelligence and temperament are the foundations of personality which are genetically determined through structure inheritance. These raw materials are then patterned to personality characteristics by environmental influences. As Buhler (1994) in Hurlock (1996) pointed out, "the successions of event which are of influence on a person's life are part of his history. They present a counter agent to the individual's own dispositions and they may be variously supportive of or detrimental to his own goal setting". The forms into which the hereditary potentials will develop will depend largely on the significant people in the individual's environment. It is they, who determine what his physical and social environment will be. It is they, who determine what opportunities the individual will have for learning and what limitations will be placed on these opportunities. While the cultural environment will provide him with approved patterns to imitate. It is the significant people in his life who will achievement in life or determine to what extent one achieves in life.

The Role of Environment on Achievements in Life

In an achievement-oriented culture, a person is judged by what his achievements are, how they compare with those of others, and how early in life he is able to attain them. If they are in an area that is highly valued by the social group, they will be more favorably judged than one who achieves more but in a less prestigious area (Hurlock, 1996) "From early in life, the achievements are attained, the more favourably the person is judge. The student who Graduates from College at 15 or 16 years is regarded as a "wonder boy". This is the label applied to the man who makes his millions before he is 40 years or who is the youngest person to be chosen for a high-status position in government, business, industry, or a profession. In time, the person comes to expect certain achievements of himself and he sets goals for their quality, quantity and timing. If not, he will feel like a failure and the effect on his self-concept will be damaged. These all depend on how the environmental factors have made them.

Obstacles of the Environment to Future Achievements in Life

Many people who are willing and able to work are kept from achieving what they are capable of by obstacles over which they have no control. For most part, these obstacles are environmental, primarily unfavourable social attitudes based on sex, race, religion or age. Women for example, rarely achieve the success they are capable of in areas outside home making. Prejudice against women exists in many occupations and in executive position in the occupations in which they have been accepted (e.g. ministerial positions, senate etc).

Despite the fact that women have broken from these shackles of men chauvinism and domineering attitude. Professor Dora Akinyilli of NAFDAC, Ngozi Okonjo Iwuala, Finance Minister to mention but a few must all go home to cook meals for their husbands, in good time too. Secondly work dissatisfaction, which contributes to poor achievements, can come from other environment factors than discrimination and unfavorable social attitudes. Studies show that workers dissatisfaction comes mostly from factors peripheral to the jobs, such as work rules, seniority rights, wages and fringe benefits. Thirdly, academic achievements are often adversely affected by lack of social acceptance. Those who are well accepted perform better than those who are neglected. Poor academic work is common among those who are resentful because they do not receive the social acceptance they crave fourthly, is the effect of failure on personality. Failure is always ego deflating. No one likes to fail, even though he may have anticipated it. Failure undermines self-confidence and, in time, destroys the person's belief that he can do anything at all well. This weakens his motivation to attempt even what he is capable of doing. Finally, poor achievement may come from the person's unfavourable attitudes towards self, from poor health, from lack of motivation and from many other subjective factors. Their attitudes deprive them of the motivation to work up to their capacities.

CONCLUSION

People's attitudes towards their achievements in life as well as the satisfaction they derive from them have more far-reaching effects on their self-concept than the achievements themselves. Again, these attitudes are influenced by the environmental factors as discussed in the paper. The paper concludes that the most significant factors in the environment appear to be those which promote an atmosphere of security, of basic trust between parent and child or teacher and pupils. Also, relations with peers, family are as important as physical needs.

RECOMMENDATION

1. There is the need for a wholesome attitude in the family toward learning and cultural experiences. This will make the parents to stimulate his interests.
2. The family should show love to their children as well as to themselves. Hostile home environment makes a child to be hostile too, but a congenial home environment brings about harmonious living within the family, bearing in mind that the nucleus of the society is the family.
3. The home and school atmospheres should provide a variety of experiences and opportunities for the recognition of the child's potential.
4. Other members of the society, in general, must per take in shaping the attitudes of the child in the society.

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